

INFORMATION ABOUT LIVER CIRRHOSIS AND TREATMENT OPTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In the treatment of liver cirrhosis, it is important to eliminate the factors that cause it. If an infection that caused liver cirrhosis is detected, measures are taken to eliminate it. To prevent liver cirrhosis, it is necessary to improve working and living conditions, and to combat alcoholism.

INTRODUCTION

Antimitochondrial antibodies (AMA) are detected in laboratory tests, the most typical of which is M2-AMA, directed against the E2 subunit of pyruvate dehydrogenase, an increase in the level of IgM in the serum. In addition, extrahepatic manifestations are mediated by immunity - Hashimoto's thyroiditis, Sjogren's syndrome, fibrosing alveolitis, tubulointerstitial nephritis, celiac disease, as well as those combined with rheumatic diseases - systemic scleroderma, rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Liver cirrhosis is a pathology in which normal cells are replaced by scar tissue. This leads to the body not being able to function normally. Toxins and bile accumulate in the liver and poison the entire body. In most cases, the disease is diagnosed in middle-aged men and retirees.

Reasons:

The main causes of liver cirrhosis are hepatitis and alcohol abuse. The following may also play a role in the development of the disease:

- autoimmune diseases;
- genetic diseases;
- chronic cholestasis (impaired bile secretion);
- obstruction of the hepatic veins.

Symptoms:

It is very important to detect this disease as early as possible. The symptoms of the disease in the early stages are as follows:

- loss of appetite, weight loss;
- general upset, headache;

- aching pain in the right hypochondrium or upper abdomen;
- enlarged spleen;
- changes in liver size (both sharp increase and decrease);
- sharp increase in abdominal cavity volume (due to fluid accumulation);
- belching, nausea, burning in the mouth, flatulence;
- urination disorders;
- enlarged blood vessels on the anterior abdominal wall;
- changes in skin tone around the navel (becomes bluish);
- appearance of red spots on the chest, back and shoulders;
- redness of the palms;
- in men: enlarged mammary glands, hair loss in the armpits and pubis, sexual dysfunction;
- in women: menstrual irregularities.

Gradually, a patient with liver cirrhosis develops jaundice, and the skin may itch.

Diagnostics:

Diagnostics are performed by specialized specialists: gastroenterologist and hepatologist.

After collecting complaints and visual examination, the patient is sent for examination:

- blood tests (biochemical, for hepatitis);
- ultrasound examination of abdominal organs;
- gastroscopy.

If necessary, additional studies are prescribed:

- radioisotope study of the liver;
- CT;
- liver biopsy.

Care:

Unfortunately, it is impossible to completely cure liver cirrhosis, but if the disease is detected in the early stages, it can be slowed down. In advanced forms of liver cirrhosis, treatment is aimed at eliminating symptoms and combating possible complications.

Treatment of liver cirrhosis is complex and includes:

- a special diet;
 - antiviral drugs;
 - hormonal agents (for autoimmune diseases);
 - drugs that have a beneficial effect on liver cells;
- plasmapheresis.

In severe cases, liver cirrhosis should be treated in a hospital.

In some cases, surgery is necessary:

- removal of fluid from the abdominal cavity (paracentesis);
- maneuver;
- liver transplant.

Prevention:

To prevent liver cirrhosis, it is necessary to:

- take care of your health;
- timely treatment of diseases that have a negative impact on the liver and lead to liver cirrhosis;
- do not abuse alcohol.

Treatment of liver cirrhosis should be carried out only under the supervision of an experienced specialist.

DISCUSSION

Over many months and years, the hepatocyte genome changes and a clone of pathologically altered cells is created. As a result, an immune-inflammatory process develops.

The following stages of liver cirrhosis pathogenesis are distinguished:

1. The action of etiologic factors: cytopathogenic action of viruses, immune mechanisms, the action of hepatotoxic cytokines, chemokines, prooxidants, eicosanoids, acetaldehyde, iron, lipid peroxidation products;
2. Activation of cell function. That is, which leads to excessive proliferation of connective tissue in the perisinusoidal space and pericellular liver fibrosis;
3. Impaired blood supply to the liver parenchyma as a result of narrowing of the vascular cavity with the development of sinusoid capillarization and ischemic necrosis of hepatocytes;
4. Cytolysis of hepatocytes, activation of immune mechanisms.

Based on the above, it is clear that when treating liver cirrhosis, it is important to eliminate the causative factors.

CONCLUSION

In this article we want to warn people that cirrhosis of the liver can be caused by alcohol consumption, and also to convey through the media that it is impossible to completely cure the disease using pharmaceuticals for correction. Of course, this improves the patient's condition, but cannot stop the progression of the disease. If the above treatment methods do not help, a liver transplant is performed (transplantation).

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